

An IoT-Based Tool-Kit Design for Soil Testing: A Sustainable Agricultural Approach

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Abstract

Rice is the world most important food crop and around 4 billion people use it as primary food. India is the second largest rice producer in international forum, which contributes around 10% of the total Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of country in agricultural, foresting and fishing sector (As per statisitcetimes.com). However, production rate needs to be improved proportionally with population of country, at the same time the challenges to rice cultivation in the country increases day by day due to quality of soil, scarcity of laborers, wages, irrigation, fertilizers, diseases, industrialization etc. The proposed work becomes mandatory to be implemented to increase the rice yields. However, the precision Agriculture (PA) is a recent technology which includes IoT, Data science, Machine and Deep learning, which can increase crop yield considerably, but using PA becomes difficult due to cost, infrastructure, expertise etc, the benefits of Precision Agricultural includes effective management of irrigation, crop diseases, crop yield, soil quality and pest control. Even though preserving ecological system is also equally important to secure next generation, environment, and health. This paper has proposed an integrated IoT based device to measure 12 primary nutrients required for rice production, which are classified as macro and micronutrients. The results of work can be used to measure the nutrients level in soil, which can help farmers to decide the volume of fertilizer to support ecofriendly environment, increase the profit of rice cultivation and maintain the soil quality as strong as possible by avoiding unwanted chemigation. The proposed work also includes the advantages of Precision Agriculture with traditional practice, together called Sustainable Agriculture (SA).

Keywords: Precision Agriculture, Soil Quality, Rice's Nutrients, Soil Sensors, Soil Testing, Sustainable Agricultural.

Introduction

The rice cultivation can be done only in the area, there is the annual rainfall is more than 1000 mm, temperature needs to be in the ranging from 20oC to 30oC and the clayey loam soil (27-40 % clay content) in monsoon land is best suit for rice cultivation. There are some issues becomes challenges to improve the rice yields in our country. The primary issues are water scarcity and salinization, particularly agriculture consumes 70% global surface water for its production, in that 30 % of water used for rice cultivation [6]. Secondly According to Directorate of economics and statistics the wages rate in 2017-2018 was Rs.500 and Rs.300 for men and women respectively in agriculture sector, especially during the peak season like transplantation and harvesting, the wages reach up to Rs.600 and Rs.350 for men and women respectively. The small landowners are not

able to get even minimum production cost from rice cultivation due to more expenditure in wages, fertilizers, and electricity etc. According to Agricultural census 2010-11, Department of Agricultural & Cooperation, Ministry of agriculture, Government of India, the land area holding by farmers can be classified as small, semi-medium, medium, and large, which means below of one Hectares around 359,08,000 Hectares (22.5 % in total land area of India) holding by small farmers (1-2 Hectares). There are 352, 44,000(22.1%) Hectares are in the hand of Semi-Medium (2-4 Ha) farmers, medium farmer (4-10 Ha) holding 33828000(21.2 %), but only 16907000(10.6 %) Hectares are in the hands of Large (>10 Ha) farmers. This work has proposed the design of a toolkit for soil testing with 12 nutrients, which are classified as macro and micronutrients. The macro nutrients are highly influences for rice cultivation and it is further classified as three more subtypes such as structural nutrients (Hydrogen-H, Oxygen-O), Primary nutrients (Nitrogen-N, Phosphorus -P, Potassium- K) and Secondary nutrients (Calcium -Ca, Magnesium -Mg). The micro elements are required in less volume these are Iron -Fe, chlorine -Cl, zinc -Zn, Nickel -Ni, Copper-Cu. The proposed tool kit can measure the available level of nutrients in any land and compare the threshold values approved by the local administration for suitability of land for rice cultivation. It also can limit the fertilizers usages by sending prescribed nutrients and chemigation to farmer registered mobile number to avoid imbalance of environment as the future work. The proposed work is to support the land holder to check the soil quality without going to the agriculture center and avoid the awaiting time for soil report. Second, according to iKisan agriculture portal, there are 20% to 50 % yield losses in India due to damage caused by various insect pest. More than 70 insects are identified as harmful to the rice among those 20 insects are more significant to control the pest, So the farmers are inclined with chemical method, which can quickly get relief. However more usages of pesticides, germicides, and insecticides will create the chance for chronic and fatal diseases like cancer, asthma [8]. But chemical control method is inevitable to produce the maximum yields in rice production. The proposed work has the threshold values which can match with permitted level of fertilizers in the area using dataset which will be added into the proposed work as future extension and Nano-robotic also planned to capture the image periodically from appropriate dimensions and send the images for further investigation in the system. So, identification of pests and deceases can be done at an early stage, and pests and diseases can be controlled with less amount of fertilizer, which can increase production, preserve the quality of soil as well as avoid the ecological imbalance. Nowadays agriculture lands are becoming a part of people crowding area due to infrastructure development such as hospitals, schools, railways, bus stand, educational intuitions etc. This work can considerably decrease the environmental pollution by limiting volume of chemigation in land and approve the chemigation based on local administration. Secondly the soil testing kit can be used easily by farmers at any time that is before cultivation and after cultivation. The landholder can maintain the quality of soil for crop yield enhancement. The proposed work is aimed at addressing the major two issues in rice cultivation facing small and medium landholders. First, identify the land suitability for paddy cultivation In connection with this, at present landholders approach the nearby agricultural center for soil testing and they need wait for soil report minimum of a week to know the land suitability. Whereas in case of implementation of proposed work, the farmers/landholder themselves can check for soil suitability anytime and the report will be displayed on kit's screen itself. Secondly, landholders spending more resources (Money, Man, Machine) to improve the yield and spray of pesticides, and fertilizers in large amount makes the environments to be more harmful to living things, water resource bases etc. This work can be extended to includes, the Nano-robotics kit design as future work, which can reduce the cost of fertilizers by periodically scouting the land for

diseases and report the same to land holders with fertilizers and its permitted level to spray, which is approved by local authorities with respect to sensitiveness of surrounding well in advance. So, the proposed work not only reduces the resources utilization cost it also can save the environment effectively so-called sustainable agriculture. Further of the paper organized as four more sessions. Session 2 deals with literature study of soil testing in national and international forums. The methodology of design of IoT-based soil testing device is elaborated in session 3. Session 4 summarized the validation, results and finding of proposed work. Finally, conclusion and future works are presented in session 5.

III. Literature Survey and Background works

With reference to a query “precision agriculture uses recent Technologies” on google search engine found numerous research works and restricted the literature survey for the work with respect to year and rice production. An article [9], proposed a framework for precision farming using IoT and regression analysis for prediction of yield using machine learning algorithm. The research also proposed a device to measure the soil moisture, CO₂, light intensity, temperature, humidity and controlled remotely using message query telemetry Transport (MQTT) and analyzed for anomalous behaviors. However, the work has supported the temperature and nutrients for growing nursery in the greenhouse using sensors and microprocessors. Second, a scalable network architecture to monitor and control agricultural fields was proposed by Ahmed et al ,2018, the work included wi-fi based long distance network and Fog computing to monitor remotely. The [11], has proposed a framework to monitor the quality of crop, yield of the crop with respect to self-pollination for papaya, the self-irrigation was used through optical sensors. The auto chemigation using spray vehicle method was recommended as the part of precision farming [3]. The Dinkins and Jones proposed a tool-kit called Lab-in-Box which is to measure only Nitrogen(N), Sulphur(S), Chloride (Cl), tool-kit can check the soil around 100 sample per day [8]. However, the proposed system includes toolkit for soil-testing with respect to 14 parameters which are essential for rice cultivation and the fertilizer recommendation will be prescribed with volume, approved by local administration, since level of fertilizer should be restricted place to place such as hospital zone, school, residential area, water sources. This eco-friendly chemigation can be done effectively using our proposed work. The major aim of the system is not only increasing the yields but also protect the ecological system. According to Government of India report, the small and marginal landholding (SLH) farmers, dominated by Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes [7], account for ~ 85% (117 million out of 138 million) of total agricultural landholders. SLHs are cultivating over 72 Mha of land. and contribute 50–60% of India’s total food requirement [20]. The major challenge to SLH is scarcity of Labour, water, fertilizers, and hike in wages. However, the precision agriculture is to incorporate the recent technologies to increase the yields, So India has established 22 Precision Farming Development Centers (PFDCs)throughout the country, which associated with various agriculture-related activities to increase the productivities such as site-specific application of irrigation, pesticides in cotton, oil palm plantation in south India. tea garden of eastern India to reduce the production cost, also reduce loading of chemicals, forecast, mitigation problem like water stress, nutrient deficiency, and pest monitoring. Even though alone with precision method there need to be a protocol to preserve the traditional practice of agriculture to protect our next generation, expand the earth’s natural resource base, maintain, and improve the soil from heavy fertilizers. So, we propose the framework using IoT to measure the essential requirement well in advance. The local

administration also can fix the threshold value based on environmental pollution (air, water, and infrastructures such as schools, hospital etc). The Nanorobotics in the framework can assess the crop health periodically and predict productivities to further processes such as marketing, price, and availability etc.

IV. Methodology and Implementation

The proposed work aims to implement precision and sustainable agriculture in rice cultivation to preserve our natural resource bases, environment, human and animal health. The work is having two devices: the First device called soil-kit, which is to measure the quality of soil with respect to 12 primaries required nutrition [4]. The required parameters are classified as macro and micronutrients. The macro nutrients are highly influences for rice cultivation and further macro nutrients have classified as three types such as structural nutrients (Hydrogen-H, Oxygen-O), Primary nutrients (Nitrogen-N, Phosphorus -P, Potassium- K) and Secondary nutrients (Calcium -Ca, Magnesium -Mg). The micro elements are required in less volume these are Iron -Fe, chlorine -Cl, zinc -Zn, Nickel -Ni, Copper-Cu. secondly a Nano-Robotic device will be scouting the cultivation area for paddy health periodically, so that if any diseases in plant it will send the information to landholder through mobile phone about diseases and prescription with permitted level fertilizer by local authorities. The proposed work aims to meet the following objectives :1. To design a device which assesses the quality of soil with respect to 12 parameters. 2. To design a Nanorobotics to capture the image of crops for health monitoring. 3. To develop an image classification system to identify the types of diseases in crops. 4. To develop the fertilizer/pesticide prescription system for identified disease with volume for chemigation based on environmental factors. 5. To design a yield prediction system to enhance production. Objective 1: To Perform quality Assessment of Soil with respect to 12 essential parameters and deciding the fertility and quantity approved by local authorities The toolkit will analyze the quality of the soil for 12 parameters, which are essential for rice cultivation. The required parameters are classified as macro and micronutrients. The macro nutrients are highly influences for rice cultivation and further classified as three types such as structural nutrients (Hydrogen-H, Oxygen-O), Primary nutrients (Nitrogen-N, Phosphorus -P, Potassium- K) and Secondary nutrients (Calcium -Ca, Magnesium -Mg). Second, the micro elements are required in less volume, which are important to metabolism of rice. these are Iron -Fe, chlorine -Cl, zinc -Zn, Nickel -Ni, Copper-Cu. The following components will be used to design a toolkit.

Components Used:

Micro Controller (ESP32 CAM/ESP32)

NPK Sensor, NTX sensor

PH sensor

EC Sensor

LM35 –temperature sensor

Humidity sensor

Soil Moisture Sensor

Soil Oxygen measuring sensor-MIJ-03.

Ethernet MAC Interface: 1

Touch Sensor: Yes.

Working Temperature: -40 °C to -125°C

Soil NPK Sensor with MAX485 Module

NPK: This sensor is used to measure the presence of Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium in the soil or Substrate and helps to predict the required amount of these values to inject as fertilizers.

NPK Specification:

Voltage: 9-24Volts

Power consumption: <0.15 Watts

Working temperature: 5-45 Celsius (41-113 F)

Baud rates: 2400, 4800, and 9600.

Measuring Resolution: 1mg/kg(kg/l)

Measuring range: 0-1999mg/kg

Accuracy: $\pm 2\%$

Communication mode: Modbus RS485

Protection rated: IP68

MAX485TTL to RS 485 Converter Module:

With the help of this MAX485 module we can communicate between RS485 differential signal from NPK sensor and Microcontrollers such as Arduino.

Max 485 module converts TTL signals to RS485.

Operates with 5v and 300 μ A.

Used for long range of Communication: 4000 feet.

Supports multiple connection: 32 devices.

Arduino Nano 33 BLE Sense:

Microcontroller nRF52840

Features a lot of sensors 9 axis Inertial Measurement

Unit (IMU), temperature, pressure, humidity, light, color, and even gestures sensors. Wi-Fi and Bluetooth enabled and runs machine learning projects.

Figure 1. Architecture of IoT-Based Tool-Kit for Soil Testing

V. Conclusion and Future Works

Nowadays agriculture lands are becoming a part of people crowding area due to infrastructure development such as hospitals, schools, railways, bus stand, educational intuitions etc. so spray of pesticides, and fertilizers in large amount makes the environments to be more harmful to living things, water resource bases etc. This work can considerably decrease the environmental pollution by limiting volume of chemigation in land and approve the chemigation based on local administration. Secondly the soil testing kit can be used easily by farmers at any time, that is before cultivation and after cultivation landholder can maintain the quality of soil for crop yield enhancement. The proposed work is aimed to address the majorly two issues in rice cultivation by small and medium landholders. First, identify the land suitability for paddy cultivation. In connection with this issue, at present landholders approach the nearby agricultural center for soil testing and they need to wait for the report a minimum of a week to know the land suitability. Whereas in case of implementation of proposed work, the farmers/landholder themselves can check for soil suitability anytime and the report will be displayed on kit's screen itself. Secondly, landholders spending more resources (Money, Man, Machine) to improve the yield. This work includes, the Nano-robotics kit, which can reduce the cost of fertilizers by periodically scouting the land for diseases and report the same to land holders with fertilizers and its permitted level to spray, which is approved by local authorities with respect to sensitiveness of surrounding well in advance. So, the proposed work not only reduces the resources utilization cost it also can save the environment effectively.

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